

From The Beer Orders to Last Orders –Legislation, Taxation and The Modern Beer Landscape of London

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Summary

This paper charts the impact of the transformative progressive beer duty tax introduced in 2002 on the brewing geography of London. We do this through an analysis of the beer itself, analysing data on over 9000 different beers brewed in the city by almost 300 different brewers. Through a careful spatial and temporal analysis of beer brewed in the city, we document the evolving new beer scene unleashed by this small stroke of fiscal creativity; a scene which reflects London's global status and showcases the planetary influences shaping one of the most exciting contemporary beer landscapes in the world.

KEYWORDS: Beer, Brewing, Spatial Analysis, London, Legislation and Taxation

1. Introduction

Today, London is home to one of the most vibrant beer scenes in the world, with hundreds of craft breweries brewing a huge diversity of beer, but we do not have to travel back very far into history to find a very different situation. At the turn of the Millennium, anyone walking into one of London's many pubs would likely be met with a small selection of mass-produced beers brewed by just one of six multinational brewers. Successive decades of gradual monopolisation in the brewing industry - acquisitions, mergers and the out-competing of smaller brewers through the advantages offered by economies of scale – alongside the control of sales through the pub-tie system, meant that by the year 2000 the once diverse beer ecosystem of the country had been reduced to lifeless monoculture with beer drinkers faced with a dreary, predictable homogeneity within most pubs.

So, what has happened in the two decades since to affect such a huge turnaround in the fortunes of the nation's and the Capital's beer story? How has the turnaround unfolded and where do we find ourselves now in terms of the volume, variety and quality of beer available in London? And what are the prospects for London's renewed global prominence as perhaps one of the most exiting beer cities in the World right today?

In this paper we will answer these questions through examining historic evolution of brewing alongside the influence of beer taxation and laws relating to the consumption of beer in the UK. This history culminates in a seismic event which was the introduction of Progressive Beer Duty in 2002. We then chart the evolution of beer and brewing in the Capital since the year 2000 using longitudinal data on beer and breweries in the city compiled by RateBeer.com, using this evidence to help review the structural and planetary forces at play today, before pondering likely prospects for the future.

2. Background

By 1989, the market for beer in the UK was dominated by six national brewers – Bass, Allied Breweries, Whitbread, Grand Met, Courage and Scottish and Newcastle (House of Commons, 2004). Between

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them these six breweries accounted for 75% of UK beer production and owned or controlled over half of the pubs in the country. The “tied house” system meant that landlords in pubs owned by the breweries were being forced by the breweries to buy their beer, limiting what could be sold to drinkers and further stifling diversity (Waterson, 2010). Government legislation known as The Beer Orders was introduced in 1989 to try and break up the monopoly and required the breweries to sell or release from their ties half of their pub estates above a threshold of 2,000 premises. However, far from releasing tenant landlords from servitude, the Beer Orders simply shifted the ownership to new, large ownership companies which became known as ‘PubCos’ who bought up many of the estates sold off by the breweries and still controlled sales.

Some small breweries still existed but were not thriving. One of the issues was that alongside the marketing and access to pubs problem, beer duty (tax) on beer produced had to be paid at the same rate regardless of who produced it and how much was produced. Where the big brewers enjoyed huge discounts on the vast volumes of brewing ingredients they purchased, the playing field was not level (SIBA, 2022). Recognising this, the Society for Independent Brewers (SIBA) and the Campaign for Real Ale (CAMRA) lobbied politicians for a change in the way beer duty was levied to benefit smaller brewers. Their pleas were heard and in 2002, Gordon Brown, the Chancellor of the Exchequer announced the introduction of a new Progressive Beer Duty. This meant smaller breweries paid far less tax on the beer they produced, levelling the playing field and paving the way for new breweries to compete with the established big six.

3. The Rise of Craft Brewing in London post-2002

Figure 1 – Growth of Breweries in London from 1999 to 2022

To observe what happened in London after 2002, we are able to take advantage of the extensive beer

data resource that is RateBeer.com. **Figure 1** shows the number of active breweries in London documented by RateBeer. As RateBeer provides information on the closure dates of some breweries, it was possible to differentiate between the number of breweries that are active, and the number of breweries being opened. At the time SBR was introduced in 2002 only three breweries of note existed in the city – Fullers (brewers of London Pride), Youngs and the recently opened Meantime Brewery in Greenwich. A small number of ‘Brewpubs’ (pubs with brewing facilities on the premises) existed at a few locations in the city alongside an equally small number of micro(craft) breweries. And this remained the situation for almost a decade, until in 2010, things change dramatically.

The emergence of the Kernel Brewery in 2009 – one of the pioneers of the new wave of craft breweries which exploded after 2010 – is really in many ways emblematic of the planetary forces at play in shaping the post-SRB landscape of beer in London. There are multiple accounts of the role that Kernel and its founder Evin O’Riordain played in the fledgling craft beer scene (Bullen, 2018; Hawkes, 2013; Spencer & Doherty, 2013) and what shines through is the important role that O’Riordain’s time in New York played in shaping his ideas, introducing, not just new beers, but new attitudes towards beer. A “culture of connoisseurship” (Bullen, 2018) which in many ways was the complete antithesis of the approach of the industrial brewer and something which carries with it the very urban connotations of Baudelaire’s flaneur – a figure who was as intrinsically cosmopolitan and well-travelled and as “sincere without being absurd” (Baudelaire, 2012, p. 9) as the evolving new cultures around artisanal approaches to beer and its consumption that Kernel would introduce to the city.

Figure 2 - Spatial distribution of breweries across London, by brewery type and number of unique beers produced, 2022.

Of course, London’s global interconnectedness through business, trade and commerce, the arts, human migration and much more has never been in doubt, but through the re-birth of a beer scene now characterised by truly global attitude serving a truly global city, we see something so very different to

what had gone before. **Figure 2** shows the spatial arrangement of these breweries today, with most located within the inner London boroughs and some noticeable clusters just south of the Thames in Bermondsey. Of particular note are the numbers of unique beers produced by these breweries. The largest circle belongs to the Kernel Brewery in Bermondsey established just over a decade ago, and can be contrasted with the Western-most commercial brewery, Fullers, at the Griffin Brewery in Chiswick, which has been brewing on that site since 1816 and which has achieved just a fraction of the unique brews that Kernel has.

Figure 3 – Breakdown of Beer Styles Brewed in London since 2000

Figure 3 breaks down each style supergroup into a proportional representation of the sub-styles within the dataset. Within the dominant ‘Anglo-American’ style, it’s clear that APA (American Pale Ale) and IPA (mostly American-style India Pale Ale, rather than more traditional IPA) dominate. The more traditional English Ordinary and Premium Bitters are still prominent alongside the Stouts and Porters for which London was originally famous, but the influence of European styles of beer is also notable. In particular, Saison (from the French for ‘Season’) and popular in Belgium is particularly prominent. It is closely related to the Sour Beer group which has seen perhaps the most rapid ascent in recent years and really demonstrates a broadening of the drinking palates of London beer drinkers beyond the styles that are historically familiar. Lagers brewed in the style of the famous German and Czech Pilsners have also played a part and indeed are the third most populous style by the end of our study period.

4. Conclusions

One creative central government policy has played a pivotal role in revitalising the British beer scene and has helped re-establish London as one of the most exciting cities in the world to drink beer. The impact of Small Brewers Relief took some time to be realised, but once a community of outward looking, experimental and passionate brewers began to emerge in London in the early 2000s, the ground had been prepared for a revolution to occur where starting a brewery became a financially viable option for anyone who wanted to do so. Our analysis reveals both the rapid growth in the city since around 2010 and an explosion of diversity reflecting influences from all corners of the beer brewing world and the important global position that London enjoys.

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Biographies

Adam Dennett is Professor of Urban Analytics and currently Head of Department at the Bartlett Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis (CASA), at University College London. Adam is a geographer with broad research interests which range from migration and mobilities, housing, gentrification, urban models and, of course, beer – all tied together with a fondness for data and computational methods.

Jakub Wyszomierski is a final year PhD researcher in the Department of Geography at University College London. His research focuses on geodemographics and capacity of spatial microsimulation techniques for the development of national geodemographic classifications with a high temporal and spatial granularity. As a part of his project, he also develops the 2021 Output Area Classification, that can ensure UK-coverage in the face of Census deharmonisation.

Steven Gray is Professor in Spatial Computation at the UCL Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis and Director of UCL Digital Humanities. He has engineered multiple award-winning systems as part of his research into social media mining using advanced distributed workflows, with his work featured in various worldwide media outlets and publications. In recent years, he has focused and specialised in research on distributed high-performance computing and analysing large datasets in real-time.

His research aims to open up new possibilities for data visualisation, collection, mining, and analysis of large scale spatial computational problems.